

Envisioning the Future of Research: 10 changes for Open Research

What do we want the future of research to look like? Who should be doing research? How should they do it? What should their motivations be? What networks and communities do we imagine? What needs to happen to get there?

Even asking these questions is simple but radical, subtle but game-changing. And they inspire further questions, related to how we would go about answering the foregoing questions. Is there an overall vision, and if so, what is it? Or, are there multiple disparate research futures that are field- or discipline-specific? *Why* do we want these changes? What's the cost of *not* doing something?

We're prone to thinking “what technology can fix this?” It's harder to think “what new social convention could fix this?”, “what new shared agreement?”, “what new norm?”, “what new conversational script template?”

Keeping in mind that fiction writers are often far ahead of everyone else in their thinking, in this paper we draw on references to speculative fiction and other historical speculative writing (listed in each section as “Further Reading”), along with contemporary work on research culture and infrastructure, to imagine potential futures for real-world science. The possibilities we consider include potential innovations across the research lifecycle¹ [[Octopus FAQ](#)] — Research Problem, Rationale/Hypothesis, Method, Results, Analysis, Interpretation, Real World Application, and Review — and beyond, to consider new institutions, new ways of working, and even new ways of thinking about research.

1. Lists of “low confidence” answers [“Research Problem”]

*A way to **identify gaps in knowledge**, and **gauge public interest and support** in a particular line of enquiry.*

Maybe in the future it might be a part of a researcher's role to browse lists of whatever the future equivalent is of Google searches or ChatGPT queries, and look at the answers that the search engine flagged as “low confidence”.

Sometimes, the researcher will know how to interpret the question better than the automated digital tool did, and may well have more up to date knowledge, meaning they could reply to the query, providing an expert answer which the original asker could be alerted to, and making it so that the next time the question was asked, it could receive a better answer. But sometimes the answer to the question might be “we don't know”, or that phrase researchers are famous for: “it depends...”. Often, it might be “we have a partial answer to this question, but we're lacking

¹https://www.octopus.ac/faq#pub_type_octopus

knowledge in this specific area". Sometimes it will be "we don't know the answer, but I think we might be able to find out by...", and at that point research projects could be born, emerging from the connection between someone asking a question and someone who has the skills, knowledge, and inclination to find an answer.

In this connection, it would be good to more closely integrate the role of the public and researchers, or to redefine it - making it less of a "us" and "them" ("the public" and "researchers"). Some foundational thinking on "citizen science" previously developed aspects of this more-integrated perspective.

With the rising popularity of AI tools, and also considering growing requirements around *explainable AI*, it will be relevant to wider populations to have a transparent view on which AI-generated answers (and methods) are low- or high-confidence, and some human guardrails to ensure that information is trustworthy and verifiable. The kinds of "openness" envisioned in the OSI's "[Open Source AI Definition](#)" would certainly help with this. There are a range of associated data governance questions currently under discussion.

References:

Alan Irwin, 1995, *Citizen Science: A Study of People, Expertise and Sustainable Development*. London: Routledge.

[Nonstarter.org](#) (archived:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20120309214350/http://www.nonstarter.org/>)

Open Source Initiative (OSI) and Open Future (2025). [Data Governance in Open Source AI: Enabling Responsible and Systematic Access](#)

Further reading: In "[Record of a Spaceborn Few](#) (Wayfarers)" by Becky Chambers, the role of archivist is explored: a keeper of knowledge which is vital to the society, but which is not gate-kept.

2. Ways for defining and clarifying problems collectively ["Research Problem"]

*A **shared framework** for describing problems and working out how they could be solved.*

Last year at the Open Science Retreat, we asked ChatGPT what it thought a day in the future of an academic might look like. Its response was depressing in multiple distinct ways. I was struck by how all the innovations were technological in nature (VR this... AI that...) - I wondered: **what innovations might be seen that are social or process-based?** An LLM will never be able to dream up new social conventions; that will likely remain a uniquely human ability for the foreseeable future.

I was reminded of a section in a book I read recently where the goodies were trying to

understand the motivations of the baddies - the goodies came together around a “logic map” (where the assumptions were laid out visually in a kind of interconnected brainstorm diagram - lots of “if this then this”) and the thing that struck me was not so much the system itself, but rather than everyone immediately knew what it was and how to use it. It was old hat.

What ways of thinking that are yet to be invented will be common by 2050? New shared frameworks of the last few decades include: Gantt charts, nudge theory, citation graphs, pomodoro technique, bullet journals, to name a few. What new frameworks could develop in the next decades? What new frameworks do we *need* to develop?

One area where I think we could benefit from collectively developing a shared framework is in problem definition and clarification: we lack common language around defining problems and the potential paths to their solutions. Developing this shared language, and making it commonplace, would enable a broader range of people to be involved in the research process - people could more quickly understand what problem a project was seeking to address, and help to work towards a solution together.

Tools and frameworks for distributed discussions (see [Loomio](#) for an example tool, and [Sociocracy](#) for an example framework) are slowly becoming more mainstream. How will society look if these concepts become commonplace enough that it can be taken for granted that a person will know how to use them?

Adapted from: [10.53962/tbp2-qxg5](#)

Reference:

Guillaume Collett. 2019. [Deleuze, Guattari, and the Problem of Transdisciplinarity](#). Bloomsbury.

Further reading:

- Rogue Protocol (The Murderbot Diaries) by Martha Wells - Goodies vs baddies
- A Half-Built Garden, by Ruthanna Emrys. In this book a voting system (shared problem definition and problem solving, but with in-built algorithms with transparently upweight those with relevant skills/experience, and upweights ideas/solutions that best align with community goals) is used to integrate the knowledge and abilities of a broad group of people in real time - allowing collective decisions to be made seamlessly.

3. Secondary data methods & analysis engine [“Methods”/“Analysis”]

A new way of asking questions and getting answers, with the explicit acknowledgment that we do not know everything.

Ways of asking questions have developed from looking up keywords in an encyclopedia, to searching for keywords in the Yahoo! directory, to using keyword searches on Google, to asking

questions in full text sentences to ChatGPT. While the answers ChatGPT gives can currently sub-optimal, the idea of asking questions is great, and could be adapted into a tool that allows anyone to ask (research) questions:

"Hey magic-answer-machine-of-the-future, what is the answer to [obscure question which hasn't been asked before]?"

The answer then is the interesting bit - we need an explicit acknowledgement that either we know something (see, for example, item 7 below) or we don't know something - and that the acknowledgment that we don't know something is fine.

"Hmm, I don't know, but I think [this] and [this] and [this] is some data that might be able to help us partially answer that question, and [these] are some people working on related things who you could contact"

This would allow the user to receive a list of useful links and potentially relevant information if they wish to pursue this further. Additionally, if we don't know the answer to the questions, this could also feed into **1 Lists of "low confidence" answers**. This could be developed to a 'co-scientist' to allow a back and forth discussion and ultimately generating a research question and analysis pipeline. Google has recently built something along these lines, and they write that, in the longer term, with increasing capacity and development, there is potential for this system to self-improve and potential to accelerate scientists' efforts to address grand challenges.

References:

Tukey, John W. (1977) *Exploratory Data Analysis*. Addison-Wesley.
Google blog posts on their recently developed "Co-scientist" [\[1\]](#), [\[2\]](#)

Further reading:

[Golem XIV](#) by Stanisław Lem

4. Confidence and respect to review openly ["Review"]

*We need to adopt a **method** like PREreview more widely.*

The purpose of PREreview is to enable everyone to "Provide and receive constructive feedback on preprints from an international community of your peers." The system is set up in such a way that it that allows for anonymity without losing accountability:

Your PREreview account will give you access to two names with which you can publish your PREreviews. One is your PREreview pseudonym which is a preassigned and uneditable combination of an animal and a color (e.g. Yellow Penguin). The other is the name corresponding to your ORCID ID (here referred to as your public name). If you choose to publish a review with your pseudonym, your public name will remain hidden

unless you disclose your pseudonym to others. — <https://prereview.org/how-to-use>

PREreview aims to re envision the way research works, “to make science and scholarship more equitable, transparent, and collaborative.” There’s precedent for this kind of visionary thinking. In 1945, Vannevar Bush wrote: “Professionally our methods of transmitting and reviewing the results of research are generations old and by now are totally inadequate for their purpose.” Given the accelerating growth of new knowledge, it’s not surprising that the same problem comes up again. Alongside PREreview there are a range of experiments that aim to address related challenges (for instance, open annotation initiatives like [TRiP](#) (including a partnership with [eLife](#)). PREreview’s model points out that the future of peer review might not just change how we work, but even change our identities as researchers.

Reference: Open Peer Review, in The Turing Way

<https://book.the-turing-way.org/communication/peer-review/peer-review-open>

Further reading:

Vannevar Bush; [As We May Think](#); Atlantic Monthly; July 1945.

5. Mandate to work publicly after PhD [“Review”]

*Imagine a new social construct where the **awarding of a PhD** became a coming of age ritual for a researcher: you now have the honor and the responsibility to **work publicly**.*

You have a badge/tick on your profile, and your profile becomes a public log of everything (well, everything professional and of potential public relevance) that you do. Importantly, you are now grown up enough, and qualified enough, to make your mistakes publicly and use them to fuel learning. PhD programs would need new training courses in how to recognise mistakes gracefully and without existential crisis, and the “public” would see researchers as human. Young humans of types not often seen in research (under-represented groups) might see those public researchers as slightly closer to them, and might see their path to becoming a researcher as more plausible. Broadly, we would expect to see an increasing tendency by research students to make their work public rather than a “cliff edge” at the time of PhD completion.

This theme also creates a mandate to work publicly *at the grant-writing stage*. If we put our ideas out in the public, others might find ways to improve them (example: our unconference session combined 5 different proposals and was awesome). Constructive critique isn’t necessarily “objective” but can be beneficially subjective & self-interested (e.g., with new teams forming around the ideas as they develop). This way of working allows formative and collegial feedback to be shared more readily post-PhD.

Note that there are rooms for some further norms to be discussed, for example, if someone goes back for further study in a new field, would they revert to a pre-PhD way of working, or

would the mandate mean "you now have the (discipline-agnostic) emotional skills to work publicly", even in a new area? That said, there is also room for discipline specific tool support to facilitate this way of working. In principle, having too much information available shouldn't be a problem, but in practice it sometimes is (see item 4 above). Some experiments like the "[Persist](#)" extension for Jupyter notebook can help track interactions with notebooks in computational terms; related ideas may be helpful in other fields (e.g., shared digital [Zettlekasten](#)?)

Some existing initiatives towards working more publicly can be found (perhaps surprisingly) in the business world, with instruments like Objectives and Key Results (OKRs) — a method for setting and sharing ambitious strategic goals. It should also be acknowledged that working in public is scary, and that there is no shortage of dystopic fiction dealing with related challenges. It would be important to design incentives around working publicly to avoid such dystopias.

References:

Jervis Anderson (1994) [Cornel West: The Public Intellectual](#). *New Yorker*.

John Doerr (2017). *Measure What Matters*. Penguin.

[Failure CV](#) - where you list all the grants you applied for but didn't get, etc. Originally from Nature. 2010, <https://www.nature.com/articles/nj7322-467a>

Further reading:

Harlan Ellison (1965) "'Repent, Harlequin!' Said the Ticktockman"

6. Who did what in the research? ["Publication"]

*A way of **recording who did what in a research project**, beyond authorship order and being mentioned in the acknowledgements.*

Authorship is one measure of recognition, but it is very opaque (what did each author do?) and in many fields the first author is assumed to have done most of the work (which may or may not be true). We need a way of crediting who has done what in a research project that values people for what they can do, rather than benefiting those who have skills valued by the system (e.g. coming up with new ideas for research) and penalising those who have skills that are not valued by the system (e.g. creating an accessible visualisation for a piece of research that makes it much more accessible).

One possible solution (suggested by Geetika Jain, personal communication) is putting interactions with scholarly documents into a blockchain ledger, so that we could keep track of things like authorship, peer reviews, citations, funding needed, and so on. If taken far enough, we wouldn't need to run any separate research assessment exercise (like the REF) because the value of research would already be documented in real time. Doing this in real time is most likely the easiest way to do this, rather than trying to do this retrospectively, which would no doubt involve some level of trying to remember who did what / guessing.

[Octopus.ac](https://octopus.ac) takes a somewhat similar but more elementary approach, breaking academic publications down across 8 publication types, which are meant to be developed in a way that builds each one on the last. Credit would go to each person who can add a link to this chain. While real-world knowledge graphs are more complex, the same underlying principle could apply more broadly.

References:

Lulin Yang, Jiaxin Pei, Lingfei Wu (2025). Writing Patterns Reveal a Hidden Division of Labor in Scientific Teams. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.14093>

Lin, Y., Frey, C.B. & Wu, L. Remote collaboration fuses fewer breakthrough ideas. Nature 623, 987–991 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06767-1>

A Manifesto for Rewarding and Recognizing Team Infrastructure Roles (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.36850/mr8>

Further Reading:

On Sprawl and Connectedness in Notetaking,
<https://justinmanley.work/projects/notegraph/index.html>

7. Everything is a publication [“Publication”]

We need to be able to assess the contents of academic work at all scales.

Building on the remarks in item **6** above: what if we had a weighted knowledge graph that covered the contents of each publication, or all publications. A connected map of ideas, concepts, theories, and facts. Take the node "circle" for example - super important and fundamental, insofar as lots of other ideas rely on it. If you come up with a new way to think about "circle" (like Euler did with $e^{i\theta}$), well done, that's likely to be important; and, indeed, evidence for the importance of new insights like this gain further importance when they are used. In principle this sort of infrastructure could be applied to keep track of individual contributions within or surrounding articles (a bit like the CREDiT taxonomy, but with higher resolution and more of a paper trail). Getting the structural ideas out of different media provides different levels of challenge, as does communicating them across media. FutureHouse (see item **9** below) is an example of a research initiative doing work along these lines, within the field of biological science.

Reference:

Nanopublications, <https://nanopub.net/>
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Microattribution#Nanopublications>
<https://www.jove.com/> - publishes videos of methods, an interesting challenge for this way of working

Further viewing/reading:

Minority Report (2002 film); cf "The Minority Report" (1956) Philip K Dick.

8. Staying up to date with your field ["Publication" (and Literature Review, conferences)]

*We need ways to manage the **massive quantity of new publications** and other research contributions that appear all the time (at an increasing rate).*

There is a high number of new "publications" every day (as mentioned already in item **4**), and possibly there will be even more in the future (item **5**). In specific fields scientists may stay up-to-date by setting alerts on specific databases or literature programs such as Pubmed, Google Scholar or Mendeley. This can be tailored based on the keywords and search terms of interest. Artificial Intelligence and Natural Language Processing may be of use in this direction.

Reading up-to-date systematic reviews and meta-analyses may also help us stay up-to-date with our field with current literature and summary metrics while the quality of the studies included is also evaluated. Machine Learning may also help in this direction but human supervision at all stages remains always the key (OpenAI Act, Article 14). Elicit and amass may help in cases or reviews (<https://elicit.com/review/>; <https://www.amass.tech/>). Attending conferences is a way to keep informed about current changes in your research. These can however be subject to socioeconomic differences and budget allowances based on differences between institutions and countries.

Serving as a reviewer for research papers can help researchers stay up-to-date with the current literature in the specific field.

References:

Kevin Buzzard:

http://www.andrew.cmu.edu/user/avigad/meetings/fomm2020/slides/fomm_buzzard.pdf

Xiaolang Luo et al., Nature Human Behaviour volume 9, pages 305–315 (2025)

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41562-024-02046-9>

"Validating AI-assisted evaluation of open science practices in brain sciences: ChatGPT, Claude, and human expert comparisons", https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/9euw8_v2

Further reading:

Ted Chiang (1991) *Understand*

Vernor Vinge (2006) *Rainbows End*

9. New types of institution

*Why should the university be the only **place** where **trusted knowledge** can be created?*

Traditional research organisations are undergoing huge change currently - with a shift to online teaching for example, but they're incredibly powerful (in terms of funding, reputation, and how ingrained they are in wider culture) that it's unlikely we'll see them disappearing anytime soon. What other types of organisations might join the research ecosystem?

Indigenous wisdom, patient groups, researchers at capitalist organisations; these sources of knowledge have been neglected as valid in the past - how do we move past this and integrate more varied organisations into the landscape of knowledge holders and creators?

Cooperatively owned organisations - owned and operated by communities rather than capitalists or governments, might provide a path forwards. In recent months in the UK we have seen the launch of the UK's first research cooperative: [Asterisk Labs](#), which builds upon the recent growth of similar projects in France over the last few years. Here we are presented with a research organisation which can prioritise the wellbeing of its members; something which is sorely needed within modern research.

This is related to but distinct from the concept of Focused research organisations (FROs) as currently implemented, although these are interesting, and probably are "early adopters" of some of the kinds of technologies that we've been talking about here, for example, FutureHouse (<https://www.futurehouse.org/>) has some interesting tech for mining literature in biology.

There are also organisations like [IGDORE](#) which operate a little bit like shell organisations that allow researchers to work with more independence than if they were employed at a traditional organisation, without the high overheads.

Sections sourced from: Research in 2050 from [OSR 2024](#).

Further reading:

- <https://www.adammastroianni.com/science-house>
- In Becky Chambers' "Monk and Robot" there is a character who runs a community hackspace - perhaps spaces like these will become future research hubs

10. Even more open

*Although it is potentially a long way off, the possibility of a **well-integrated open research infrastructure** — something like a socio-technical operating system for research — is entirely plausible.*

Once it's created, such a system would never be finished.

Currently, a multitude of tools and practices exist that can support open, rigorous, and reproducible research practices, and more are being created all the time. Several organizations have compiled lists of resources relevant to specific initiatives; still other initiatives have

approached these issues in a more integrative way. For example, the FORCE11 project on the Future of research communications and e-scholarship worked to “produce decision trees that can help those who are interested in abiding by the principles of the commons to help achieve commons compliance.” However, despite the existence of these lists and initiatives — and indeed, evidenced by their manifold existence — knowledge about open tools and workflows is fragmented; and workflows are often not harmonised. The report on Data Governance for Open Source AI (referenced in item **1**) references the benefits of “establishing stronger ties with organizations and experts working in other fields of openness”.

What’s particularly needed here may be new “psychological infrastructure”. Our preparedness to work in an open and collaborative way can be scaffolded by “tools”, but without the corresponding attitudes, it would be quite a sterile arrangement.

Reference:

Richard Stallman (1983) [Initial Announcement of the GNU Project](#).

Further Reading:

- Jack Williamson (1947) "With Folded Hands" cf. [These are all the times sci-fi writers predicted the future](#) The Big Issue, 4 May 2025.